

Characterization of halogenated azo compounds : A parametric method 3 (PM3) study

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Abstract : Azoxy compounds of the type XN(O)NY (diazene oxides) and XNN(O)Y with organic substituents X and Y are known for their potential biological activities. In the present work, fluorinated and chlorinated azo-compounds [CF₃N(O)NF and CCl₃N(O)NCl] have been characterized by PM3 method. The isomers of CF₃NN(O)F (*cis*- and *trans*-) are more stable than CF₃N(O)NF isomers (*cis*- and *trans*-) by about 17 kcal mol⁻¹. The *trans*-CH₃NH(O)H is found to be more stable than C₈-CH₃N(O)NH by about 13 kcal mol⁻¹. Similarly *trans*-CCl₃NN(O)Cl predicted to be stable than *cis*-CCl₃NN(O)Cl by about 10 kcal mol⁻¹. The results obtained are in good agreement with other high level theoretical estimates.

Keywords : Azoxy compounds, *cis-trans* isomers, relative stability.

Azoxo compounds of aN(O)Nb with organic substituents 'a' and 'b' have been of great importance because of their biological activities¹. In the present work, we report the calculated values of heats of formation, binding energies, dipole moments and hardness of various *cis*- and *trans*-isomers of XN(O)NY and XNN(O)Y, where X and Y are H, F, Cl atoms. Hypervalent structure has been used for our results and discussion.

Since, azoxy compounds exist in two isomeric forms, XN(O)NY and XNN(O)Y, and can possess *trans*-(E) or *cis*-(Z) conformation. Full geometry optimizations for all the molecules have been performed by using MM⁺ and PM3 methods. The convergence limit was fixed at 0.01 kcal Å/mole, and all these calculations have been done by using Hyperchem (standard 5.1) software².

Results and discussion

The azoxy compound seems to exist as the CX₃N(O)NY isomer, although quantum mechanical calculations (semiempirical/*ab initio*) predict the CX₃NN(O)Y isomer to be lower in energy ranging from about 4.0 to 19 kcal mol⁻¹ depending on the various substitutions of H, F and Cl atoms in place of X and Y.

Structural analysis :

Fluoro-azoxy compound :

The calculated geometrical parameters of CF₃N(O)NF and CF₃NN(O)F isomers (*cis* and *trans*) are shown in Fig. 1 using PM3 method and are in good agreement with other high-level theoretical estimates³.

The N=N bond is shortened by about 0.02 Å when going from CF₃N(O)NF to CF₃NN(O)F, and is expected to be due to bonding of oxygen and fluorine on the same N-atom. The polarization of charges are balanced by CF₃ group on the N-atom, which is further confirmed by the lengthening of N-F (0.04 Å) and shortening of N=O and C-F bonds (0.017 Å). The bond angle variations are upto 12° in CF₃N(O)NF and CF₃NN(O)F structures. The calculated energetic parameters are shown in Table 1. The CF₃NN(O)F is more stable than CF₃N(O)NF by about 17 kcal mol⁻¹. In the CF₃N(O)NF isomer, the *trans*-conformer is about 0.6 kcal mol⁻¹ lower than the *cis*-form whereas in CF₃NN(O)F, the *cis*-form is lower than *trans*-form by 0.91 kcal mol⁻¹, which is in close agreement with high level B3LYP/6-31G* calculations³. The dipole moment and chemical hardness (HOMO-LUMO gap) values have also been reported though no trend is seen in establishing the stability of these isomers.

Fig. 1. Bond lengths in angstroms and bond angles in degrees. The values in parentheses are from high level quantum chemical calculations (B3LYP/6-31G*) and have been taken from Reference [3].

Fig. 2. Bond lengths and bond angles in angstroms and degrees respectively.

Table 1. Energetics and electronic parameters of XN(O)NY and XNN(O)Y isomers [X, Y = H, F, Cl]

System	Conformation	Heat of formation (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Binding energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Dipole moment μ (Debye)	Hardness, η (eV)
CF ₃ N(O)NF	<i>cis</i>	-115.68	-647.70	1.728	10.13
	<i>trans</i>	-116.59	-648.60	1.222	10.12
CF ₃ NN(O)F	<i>cis</i>	-134.33	-666.34	1.358	10.87
	<i>trans</i>	-133.74	-665.75	1.352	10.91
CCl ₃ N(O)NCl	<i>cis</i>	24.57	-547.83	3.990	9.26
	<i>trans</i>	18.19	-554.21	1.491	9.05
CC ₃ NN(O)Cl	<i>cis</i>	16.42	-555.98	1.715	9.08
	<i>trans</i>	14.11	-558.30	1.492	9.07
CH ₃ N(O)NH	<i>cis</i>	34.32	-630.54	5.110	10.67
	<i>trans</i>	28.19	-636.67	2.378	11.00
CH ₃ NN(O)H	<i>cis</i>	27.72	-637.14	4.658	10.39
	<i>trans</i>	21.10	-643.75	1.369	10.51
CF ₃ N(O)NCl	<i>cis</i>	-115.50	-657.61	2.40	9.46
	<i>trans</i>	-120.46	-662.57	0.546	9.27
CF ₃ NN(O)Cl	<i>cis</i>	-125.15	-667.26	1.847	10.07
	<i>trans</i>	-128.13	-670.24	2.636	10.09
CCl ₃ N(O)NF	<i>cis</i>	25.58	-536.63	3.656	9.87
	<i>trans</i>	21.31	-540.99	2.991	9.90
CCl ₃ NN(O)F	<i>cis</i>	9.48	-552.83	1.517	9.64
	<i>trans</i>	8.36	-553.94	0.374	9.58

CCl₃N(O)NCl isomers :

The calculated geometries of CCl₃N(O)NCl and CF₃NN(O)Cl isomers have been shown in Fig. 2. The experimental or high level Hartree-Fock results are not available for comparison. Since, the calculated values for CF₃N(O)NF and CF₃NN(O)F isomers from PM3 method (present work) are in close agreement with other theoretical estimates, we may, therefore, conclude that the geometric parameters of chloro-azoxy compounds predicted to be precise. The energetics of these isomers (Table 1) shows that CCl₃NN(O)Cl and CCl₃N(O)NCl are endothermic, unlike exothermic fluoro-azoxy compounds. The CCl₃NN(O)Cl isomers are relatively stable than CCl₃N(O)NCl by about 4 to 8 kcal mol⁻¹. *trans*-CCl₃NN(O)Cl is predicted to be stable by 10.0 kcal mol⁻¹ than its *cis*-form. This is in contrast with CF₃NN(O)F conformers where *cis*-form is the lowest in energy. One important aspect is noted in Table 1 regarding the dipole moment values, the dipole moment is lower for stable isomer.

CH₃N(O)NH isomers :

These isomers are found to be endothermic (Table 1) like chloro-azoxy compounds. Here also, CH₃NN(O)H isomers are more stable than CH₃N(O)NH. *trans*-form of CH₃NN(O)H is the lowest in energy and about 13.0 kcal mol⁻¹ lower than the *cis*-form of CH₃N(O)NH (similar to chloro-isomers but opposite to fluoro-isomers). The *cis*- and *trans*-forms of CH₃NN(O)H are more stable than CH₃N(O)NH by about 7.0 kcal mol⁻¹. Dipole moment values and hardness parameters also indicate the similar observation.

CF₃N(O)NCl and CF₃NN(O)Cl :

These mixed isomers are predicted to be exothermic, similar to fluoro substituted isomers (Table 1). It is interesting to note that when N-F bond is replaced by N-Cl in both isomers, the stability decreases in comparison to CF₃N(O)NF and CF₃NN(O)F isomers. The *trans*-form of CF₃NN(O)Cl isomer is predicted to be lowest in energy and about 13.0 kcal mol⁻¹ lower than the *cis*-form of CF₃N(O)NCl. In the CF₃N(O)NCl and CF₃NN(O)Cl, the *trans*-form of these isomers are about 5.0 and 8.0 kcal mol⁻¹ lower than their *cis*-form respectively. This

observation is similar to the chloro-azoxy compounds (discussed earlier). Dipole moment and hardness values though reported however, do not give any conclusive result about their relative stability.

CCl₃N(O)NF and CCl₃NN(O)F :

The calculated energetics for these isomers are reported in Table 1. Here, the C-F bonds are replaced by C-Cl bonds keeping N-F bond intact. These isomers are found to be endothermic, in close proximity with chloro-azoxy isomers. The CCl₃NN(O)F isomers are lower in energy in comparison to CCl₃N(O)NF isomers. *trans*-form of CCl₃NN(O)F is lowest in energy and about 17.0 kcal mol⁻¹ lower than *cis*-form of CCl₃N(O)NF. The *trans*-forms of CCl₃N(O)NF and CCl₃NN(O)F are more stable than their *cis*-forms by 4.0 and 1.1 kcal mol⁻¹ respectively.

Conclusion :

The semiempirical method (PM3) can be successfully applied in characterizing the molecular structures of halogen substituted azo compounds. The trends for the stability of the *trans*-isomers in chloro, mixture and unsubstituted compounds are different from those of fluoro azoxy compounds, in which the *cis*-form is stable than *trans*-form. It is inferred from the present study that the replacement N-F bond by N-Cl bond, lowers the stability of CF₃N(O)NCl and CF₃NN(O)Cl but remains exothermic, whereas, in case of C-F bond replacement by C-Cl bond keeping the N-F bond intact, the resultant mixed isomer shows increased relative stability in CCl₃NN(O)F in comparison to CCl₃NN(O)Cl. This observation is peculiar and requires further study.

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